

MEDICAL SCIENCES

CLINICAL ANATOMY OF THE CAVERNOUS SINUS

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Abstract

The article provides an analysis of literature concerning the clinical anatomy of the cavernous sinus. The significance of the cavernous sinus, its localization, structural features of the walls, and topographic properties are described based on literary materials. Particular emphasis is placed on research work devoted to the vascular and neural relationships of the cavernous sinus.

Keywords: cavernous sinus, anatomy, cranial nerves, cadaver.

The cavernous sinus receives venous blood from the lower surfaces of the frontal and parietal lobes and the superior and inferior petrosal sinuses. This is a paired venous canal located on the sides of the body of the sphenoid bone and the pituitary gland. The cavernous sinus extends from the superior orbital fissure to the petrous part of the temporal bone. The anatomical location of the cavernous sinus is unique: its localization in the middle cranial fossa, i.e., directly in the center of the skull, creates conditions for topographic proximity to a number of vital brain structures and also turns the sinus into the main collector that collects blood from the organ of vision. The cavernous sinus contains the carotid artery and some of its branches; cranial nerves III, IV, VI, and V1; and transmits venous blood from several sources. Diseases of the orbital apex and cavernous sinus usually involve multiple cranial nerves, consistent with the complex anatomy of this region. The anatomy of the cavernous sinus is complex due to the high density of critical neural and vascular structures. Individual cases demonstrate how detailed knowledge of the anatomy of the cavernous sinus can lead to safer surgery with low morbidity [1–3].

In addition, a powerful receptor apparatus localized in the wall of the cavernous sinus can affect blood flow in other sinuses. Being a complex anatomical complex, the cavernous sinus combines various formations in structure and, most importantly, in origin. These formations, according to [4], include (based on 228 preparations):

1. cavernous capsule formed by the plates of the dura mater;
2. proper venous sinus, the walls of which are formed by endothelium and connective tissue;
3. part of the internal carotid artery located inside the sinus;

4. cranial nerves;

5. forming the "stroma" of the sinus, intrasinus connective tissue developed to one degree or another.

The cavernous capsule is formed by dense bundles of collagen fibers. In most preparations, the cross-section of the cavernous capsule is in the form of a right triangle; only 14 specimens had a quadrangular shape, and 11 specimens had a cross-section of the cavernous capsule in the form of an obtuse triangle. The second form was more often determined on preparations with a deep (more than 3 cm), and the third form was determined on preparations with a shallow cranial fossa (less than 3 cm). The structure of the venous sinus itself is distinguished by a very large anatomical diversity. On some preparations, it looks like a wide venous lacuna, while on others, it is defined as a venous plexus.

An increase in the number of possible pathological processes in the cavernous sinus (aneurysms, carotid-cavernous fistulas, and various tumors) poses the problem for morphologists of a more in-depth study of the walls of the sinus and clarification of all their clinical and anatomical variants [5–6]. From this point of view, the lateral wall of the cavernous sinus is of greater importance in surgical interventions. It should be noted that the analysis of the literature indicates that there is no consensus regarding the lateral wall of the cavernous sinus. Thus, according to [7], the lateral wall consists of superficial and deep plates. III, IV cranial nerves and the ophthalmic and maxillary branches of the trigeminal nerve pass from the deep plate of the lateral wall of the sinus [8].

[9–10] in their studies pointed to the formation of the lateral wall by two plates and the passage of the III and IV cranial nerves and the ophthalmic and maxillary branches of the trigeminal nerve between these plates. The study [11] indicates that the lateral wall consists of

two plates: the superficial plate is formed by the dura mater and is smooth, and inside the deep plate are III, IV cranial nerves and the ophthalmic branch of the trigeminal nerve. These plates are connected loosely and can be easily separated.

[12] identified a triangular space bounded above by the III and IV cranial nerves and below by the ophthalmic and abducens nerves; the paper points out the importance of this triangle in surgical interventions on the internal carotid artery and its branches.

Knowledge of the anatomy of the cavernous sinus, obtained from the endoscopic view of a cadaveric autopsy, is an important step in training in endoscopic skull base surgery. It has great importance for the endoscopic treatment of various pathologies in this area [13–15]. A study of the arterial microanatomy of 24 cavernous sinuses showed that in 18 cases (75%), a meningohypophyseal trunk was present, with its origin from the intracavernous portion of the internal carotid artery. Of the 18 presented cases with meningohypophyseal trunk, 14 (77.7%) had a trifurcated pattern, and 4 (23.3%) had a bifurcated pattern. The tentorial artery was present in all [16]. In 64% of cases, the tentorial artery of Bernasconi-Cassinari arose as one branch, and in 36%, two or more branches took direct origin from the main trunk [17]. The current literature lacks a detailed map of the origin, course, and relationships of the medial tentorial artery (MTA) of Bernasconi-Cassinari, which is often involved in various diseases such as dural arteriovenous fistulas of the skull base, stenotic lesions of the internal carotid artery, saccular infraclinoid intracavernous aneurysms, and tentorial meningiomas. The artery of Bernasconi and Cassinari is an important vascular conduit for a variety of neoplasms and vascular malformations near the tentorium cerebellum. In the era of advanced microneurosurgical techniques and superselective endovascular interventions, morphometric knowledge of this artery is important for the precise and safe treatment of these lesions [18–19]. According to [20], even in the era of enormous development in microneurosurgery and endoscopy, the cavernous sinus is a complex anatomical area for the neurosurgeon. Many transcranial and several endoscopic cadaveric studies have been performed to study the cavernous sinus; probably none of them was undertaken to study its microsurgical and endoscopic anatomy in parallel. Microscopic and endoscopic detection of cavernous sinuses in cadavers is relatively easy. However, endoscopic or microsurgical exposure of the cavernous sinus during surgery is more complex and requires skill. Having experience in cadaveric examination, the cavernous sinus can be examined using transcranial microsurgery, endonasal endoscopy, or both methods simultaneously, depending on the nature and extent of the pathology.

Due to the complex multilevel architecture of the cavernous sinus, there is not always a correspondence between the surgical corridors limited by the transcranial route and those exposed by the endoscopic transnasal approach. However, some surgical corridors specific to the endoscopic transnasal route are evident: a C-shaped corridor is found medial to the “intracavernous” internal carotid artery, while a wider triangular region is found lateral to the internal carotid artery; within

the latter, three more surgical corridors can be described (superior triangular space, superior quadrangular space and inferior quadrangular space) [21].

Thus, the study of the cavernous sinus continues using classical and new research methods. A review of the literature shows the extreme relevance of these studies, both theoretically and, in particular, clinically.

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